

A Robust Image Vector Quantization Transmission System with an Embedded Degradation Control Mechanism

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a vector quantization (VQ) transmission system that both has a mechanism for detection and correction quantization artifacts, and is channel-robust, in the sense that provides some degree of immunity against channel noise. The basic idea of the source coding scheme is to treat separately the blocks whose direct quantization generates a high level of degradation. They are reconstructed via an interpolating procedure that exploits the spatial correlation in the image. The protection against the channel noise is provided by an appropriate index assignment (IA) procedure, based on Hadamard transform.

1 Introduction

Vector quantization has become a popular tool of compressing audio, image and video [7, 8]. This method is attractive mainly due to its simplicity and flexibility. In the case of image coding, a VQ coder consists of a set of reproduction blocks (codebook) and a mapping rule, that associates to each block of pixels in the image an entry in the codebook (codeword) [7, 11]. The coder maps each block to a codeword. The compressed image is represented by the corresponding codeword indices, and the decoder receives the indices and operates like a table lookup on the codebook. The elements of the VQ are designed so that to minimize a given distortion between the original image and the reconstructed one. The subjective quality of the reconstructed image depends essentially on the number of entries in the codebook and on the block size, which determine the bit rate. The inherent difficulty is to find a trade-off between the two conflicting goals: good reconstruction quality and low bit rate.

The main limitation of VQ is the blocking effect, which appears in most of block-based compression schemes. However, this effect is less annoying than in other simple coding techniques such as, for example, Block Truncation Coding (BTC) [5]. Another drawback, common to the majority of compression schemes, is that the distortion measure used in the codebook design is not correlated with subjective quality which is

the ultimate judgment of any compression method.

The idea of coding separately blocks with highly differing perceptual importance has been already used by Vasey and Gersho [12]. However, in their method the block size is variable depending on its nature. This makes the implementation more complex in the case of structured images. To overcome this difficulty they used a quadtree data structure which unavoidably increases the amount of overhead information needed to decode the blocks. Furthermore this hierarchical decomposition of the image requires an interpolation at the decoding step.

In our scheme, no extra information is needed and the bit rate is unchanged with respect to classical LBG, we just trade an entry in the codebook for the escape signaling. The blocks labeled by escape index are reconstructed from neighboring blocks, trying to efficiently exploit the local spatial dependency.

When codeword indices are transmitted over a noisy communication channel, channel noise may induce erroneous index values. Index assignment is the technique used to specify the indices for each entry in the codebook, so that to cope with the channel errors in the most effective way. Intuitively, indices which are likely to be interchanged at the decoder due to the channel noise should correspond to close enough codewords (under a given distortion measure). Without introducing additional redundancy in the transmitted data, IA procedures improve the performance of a VQ transmission system over noisy channels and do not affect the VQ performance when the channel is lossless. Here we apply a technique based on factorization of the matrix of channel block transition probabilities using Hadamard transform [9].

2 Degradation analysis

In this section we investigate the possible degradations caused by VQ and channel noise, and discuss possible ways of reducing them. The analysis is done mainly from a perceptual point of view, emphasizing the relations between subjective quality assessment and objective distortion measures.

2.1 VQ degradation

Generally VQ distortions appear when the reconstruction of a given block is a bad representative leading to degradation of fine structures. This often happens near object contours where the signal varies abruptly. The noise introduced by the VQ is highly correlated to the signal, so its analysis should be done with respect to the different local characteristics in the image.

One of the most encountered degradation in image coding methods is the blocking effect. There have been identified three kinds of blocking effect [13]: block edginess, that is more visible in homogeneous regions due to Mach band phenomenon which accentuates perceptible luminance near two adjacent homogeneous regions [4], staircase effect, which essentially appears along object contours, and the effect visible at block corners, where a pixel becomes much larger or much smaller than its neighbors. It is worth noticing that the visual perception of this degradations is not correlated with the quantitative measure of distortion such as PSNR [6] and nowadays, in spite of the great number of research efforts for developing objective image quality measure incorporating the human perception mechanisms, an efficient objective quality measure for images is not yet available [1].

LBG codebook analysis for small codebooks

Let us assume that the entries in the codebook are equiprobable, i.e. each of the N codewords is the representative of N_b/N blocks, where N_b is the number of blocks in the image. If the block size is comparable to the size of edge transitions, we may suppose that the number of image blocks corresponding to monotonic regions (small variance), N_s , is much larger than the number of block containing edge pixel (high variance), N_e . If $N_b/N \gg N_e$, the reconstruction blocks will have small variance, as the training set is mostly formed of smooth blocks. The texture blocks (high variance) either get their own reproduction (if there is a texture predominant in the image), or they migrate in different quantization cells, "dominated" by monotonic blocks. Accordingly, the most important degradations (both in terms of perceptual quality and mse) appear while reconstructing edge blocks. Thus a coding method that identify the edge blocks and reconstructs them by an interpolation procedure from the neighboring block may reduce the degradation.

2.2 Channel noise

The channel noise affects the transmitted indices, by randomly switching the bit values. This effect results in erroneous reconstructed blocks. As the induced degradation is random, and the cause (channel noise) is independent on the transmitted signal, global objective measure, such as the PSNR, would be correlated with visual perception.

In our approach, we use a binary channel with memory, modeled on contagion [2]. There are only three parameters in the model: M is the "memory" of the channel, ε is the bit error rate, and δ determines the correlation between errors at different time instances.

3 System Description

The VQ transmission system consists of source coding, IA module, transmission channel, IA^{-1} module, source decoding. IA is a permutation of the indices (labels) provided by coding module, and IA^{-1} is the inverse permutation. We send the binary representation of the indices through the binary discrete channel.

In the coding process, the blocks featuring high distortions are identified and label by an escape index. Whenever the decoder receives the escape index, it reconstructs the block from neighboring blocks, using some simple rules. The index assignment provides protection against channel noise.

3.1 Coding/decoding

For n -bit indices, the codebook has $N = 2^n - 1$ entries and is designed using LBG algorithm [3]. The first step in the coding procedure is partitioning the block set in two classes: the first is composed of blocks having low distortion, w.r.t. a given threshold, and the second corresponds to the complementary set, i.e. the set of blocks with a risk of degradation (Esc-blocks). At the quantization step, the blocks in the former class are quantized and labeled via the codebook, and the Esc-blocks are labeled by an escape index (the one not used for indexing the codebook).

If the decoder receives an index from the codebook, it looks up the codebook and outputs the corresponding entry. When the escape index is received, an escape reconstruction procedure is called to synthesize the current block. Depending on the number and location of the closest neighbors which are Esc-blocks, we use linear or nonlinear interpolation to reconstruct the block from the neighbors which are not Esc-blocks.

We will refer to our source coding procedure as EscLBG.

3.2 Index assignment

The IA is designed so that to minimize the mean square distortion between the coded and reconstructed image introduced by the channel noise. The implemented algorithm is based on Hadamard transform of the codewords. It requires the knowledge of block transition probabilities of the channel, and of the codebook. The procedure is extensively described in [9].

As the indices are n -bit integers, we provide to the IA algorithm the $2^n - 1$ codebook and the codebook center as the codeword corresponding to the escape index.

4 Results and Discussion

We present here the results obtained for 128×128 Lenna image (Fig. 1a).

The binary transmission channel is modeled on contagion, with $\varepsilon = 0.01$, $\delta = 10$, $M = 1$.

To implement EscLBG, the image was divided into 2×2 blocks. A 31-entry codebook was trained using Lenna image. The value of the threshold on the distortion was set so that approximately $1/32$ of the image blocks are Esc-blocks (see Fig. 1b). The applied index assignment was obtained using the Hadamard Switch Algorithm [9]. The reconstructed image is shown in Fig. 1d.

For comparison, we coded the image using a 32-entry codebook trained using LBG, and send the resulting indices, without applying any index assignment, over the same channel. The reconstructed image is shown in Fig. 1c.

From the point of view of the protection against channel noise, the effectiveness of the IA technique is clearly demonstrated through this example. The PSNR increase of Fig. 1d with respect to Fig. 1c is due to the capacity of the index assignment to reduce the effect of the channel noise. PSNR measure correlates well with visual perception of channel noise effect, since the degradation affects the signal in a random manner.

Regarding the quantization artifacts, at the first glance Fig. 1d and Fig. 1c do not present noticeable differences due to masking effect [10]. Even if classical LBG would lead to a better PSNR in the absence of channel noise (approx. 1 dB), our method improves the perceptual quality of the image. If we focus our comparison on marked blocks, one can clearly observe more staircase effect in Fig. 1c than in Fig. 1d, see for example the shoulder and top-right side of the hat. To point out these differences a region of interest (top-right side of the hat) is zoomed and shown in Fig. 2. Remark that these images are obtained under noise-free conditions on the channel. Not only the staircase effect is visible but also the corner outlier which are more accentuated in Fig. 2b than in Fig. 2c.

5 Conclusions

In this contribution, we propose a robust and efficient vector quantization system which copes with both channel noise and quantization effect. The obtained results show that the VQ using IA allows to trade off low bit rate with image quality without increasing the size of the codebook with overhead information as in other comparable approaches, and providing protection against the channel noise at the same bit rate. Our current line of research is centered on designing some forms of objective measures of image quality which correlates with human visual perception in order to efficiently detect degraded blocks. More elaborated strategy, where blocks are classified as texture, monotonic and edge could be incorporate in the system. An adaptive scheme for re-

constructing such block is also under investigation and will be applied in a near future.

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a. Original (128×128 pixels)

b. Esc-blocks marked on original

c. Reconstruction – LBG and no IA ($PSNR = 27.05dB$)

d. Reconstruction – EscLBG and IA ($PSNR = 28.80dB$)

Figure 1: The combined effect of channel noise and quantization on the reconstructed image. The image is divided into 2×2 blocks, which are coded via a 32-entry codebook (LBG), or a 31-entry codebook (EscLBG). The indices are sent over a channel modeled on contagion, with $\varepsilon = 0.01$, $\delta = 10$, $M = 1$. An IA is performed on the indices obtained using EscLBG.

a. Escape blocks

b. LBG ($N = 32$)

c. EscLBG ($N = 31$)

Figure 2: Zoom in the top-right region of the hat (error-free channel)